

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NJEI****FIRST NAME: BASILE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied XUS UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Mac)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)
4. Latin Expressions and Abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)
5. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
6. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2019, 49-55)
7. Quotation Marks (EUCLID 2019, 6-7)

REMOVING THE COMPLEXITY IN ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Though I have written many papers throughout my academic years, EUCLID's course, ACA-401D period one, enlightens my understanding of essay writing basics. This course demonstrates the main themes when writing a good essay; it is detailed and highly informative. It shines a light on how to format and structure your "Style" and the specific language you will be using (for instance, using styles for RP Head 1, RP Head 2, RP Head 3, RP Normal, RP Quote, RP Reference, and RP Title). The U.K format is different from the U.S format, so the rule of style and your essay's organization is essential because it helps explain how to make citations and references using the specific language rule. Assisting the students in supporting the main points with reason, details, also, paying attention to sources, punctuation marks, and quotations are essential tools to use when writing your essay. Having a style will help you know how to use capitalization, punctuations, and more (EUCLID 2019, 1-4).

I had many doubts before taking this course. The introductory video and ACA-401D period one coursepack instructions have given me a feeling of confidence and a better understanding of how-to-write an excellent essay in American English. The information provided for this course, the templet, the use of technology are great starting tools. Being organized and writing my own superbly detailed essay, spelling out the facts, analysis, evidence, and drawing conclusions may seem complicated. Still, this course has provided me with all the material I need to be a successful writer.

2) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is representing another author's language, thoughts, ideas, or expressions as one's original work. In ACA-401D course pack, using someone else's information and not giving them credit or stating the author's name is unacceptable and an act of plagiarism. Copying someone else's idea word for word without acknowledging them must be avoided (EUCLID 2019, 5, 16). When writing an essay, always remember to cite and acknowledge the exact author of a particular statement, either "In-Text Citation," where we must indicate the authors last name and the year of publication for the source, for example, (James 2003) or by the list of works cited. On the other hand, we are also introduced to Quotations, the introduction to Quotations is defined as a sentence, phrase, or passage taken from a text, speech, and repeated by someone other than the original author or speaker. Quotations present a well-known statement attributed by citation, a note, or parenthetical citation to their source; such statements are captured by quotation marks or indented as a blockquote (EUCLID 2019, 48).

Many researchers have proven that students plagiarize almost all the time when writing their essays. It could be due to ignorance or negligence; whatever the case, there is no excuse; even unintended plagiarism is prohibited and not excused. However, students get caught up in their writing and the rephrasing and paraphrasing decisions they make, which comprises plagiarism and sometimes this happens due to the lack of understanding of how and when to rephrase or paraphrase someone else's point of view while avoiding plagiarism. Defusing the meaning of *rephrasing* and *paraphrasing* helps bring a better understanding of the issue related to plagiarism. The EUCLID course package documentation excellently clarifies this point.

Despite this, there are several ways to avoid Plagiarism. First, it is vital to organize or plan your paper; this will give you a clear vision about your assignment and gives you a lesser chance of consulting another person's material. It is also important to cite the sources used to prepare for the paper and keep the originals in the correct context. You must match the objective of your paper to achieve meaningful material. Learn not to cut and paste, as it gives a wrong unethical impression of any study paper.

"Paraphrase" is when you put someone else's ideas in your own words and provide only a citation without quotation marks. Paraphrasing is useful because you sometimes do not want your essay filled with many quotes; it makes your paper look unrepresentable. A

student may have to paraphrase a sentence to give the reader a better view and eye by looking different from the authors' exact words. Let us look at an example of paraphrasing with an original text from dictionary.com. The original message may look like this, "Symptoms of influenza include fever and nasal congestion." The paraphrase will be, "a sniffy noes and high temperature are signs you may have the flu." However, if you translate a text from another language, you need to cite the reference to avoid taking someone else's ideas, hence plagiarism. On the other hand, rephrase manipulates someone's exact words, opinions, or concept to different but synonymous terms, thereby changing the details originality and crossing the thin line, leading to plagiarism.

Nevertheless, it is acceptable not to cite obvious and information statements that are everywhere; for instance, writing a message such as "sunscreen should be used in the summertime to avoid sunburn." There is no need for citing this information because it is stating something known. For this reason, there is a format to follow when citing the original author. For example, Gerson, Steven. 2009. *Technical communication Process and product*. Upper Saddle River. Pearson (Authors Name. Date. Book Title. Place of Publication: Publisher). Footnotes, on the other hand, have a different format, for example: After punctuation, do insert>Reference>Footnote reference (in Word, 2003) or References>Insert footnote (In Word 2007). Make sure you use footnotes, not endnotes. Here's an example of a footnote: Citation styles such as Chicago A, OSCOLA, Turabian, and ACS require the use of footnote citations instead of author-date in-text citations.

3) STYLE GUIDE

When writing EUCLID papers, I need to follow the *Turabian style* of formatting books and academic papers extracted from the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS). In Dr. Abel Scribe's *CMS Crib Sheet*, she explained that the *Turabian style* of formatting in the *Turabian's Manual for Writers* applies Chicago Style to "research papers, theses, and dissertations," that is, final manuscripts (EUCLID 2019, 44, 49). The CMS Crib Sheet in the course pack expands my knowledge on Chicago Style and Usage, Chicago page formatting, and Chicago End/Footnotes. Dr. Scribe further expatiates on these sub-topics, and I recognize several points, which includes that; the use of quotation when quoting material in a foreign language must have all its exact accents and other marks as they appear in the originals; (for example, école, tête, leçon, años, Fähre) (EUCLID 2019, 48).

As a result, paying attention to margins, spacing, headers, fronts, indents are essential points to note when writing using Chicago page formatting. The Margins must be one inch on all four edges of the page. On the other hand, fonts can be categorized depending on their characteristics that have emerged through history. Twelve-point type (ten characters per inch) for text and ten-point (twelve characters per inch) for notes will meet requirements for most institutions" (Turabian 1996, 7,8-24). EUCLID has provided templates to make this process easy, accurate, and organized. I am required to ensure my report is by the style that is needed. A good essay will be a good paper with no grammatical errors and a useful vocabulary; it must be persuasive and detail-orientated to the audience and the readers. It will improve communication and make it easy to ensure consistency in

my writing and my knowledge. A style guide will provide me with objective and creative results.

Moreover, I embrace that having a style manual ensures that your writing is consistent and coherent, especially when dealing with publications or companies with many contributing authors. Writing for a different audience entails you to follow the rules because different audiences require different needs. Conforming to a discipline-specific writing style helps your work “fit in.” Organizing your work before starting your essay is particularly important because you will need to have all your essay points supported and the evidence to back it up. Using a style will also give you an overview and insight into what you will talk about, and how you will go about it: What figure of speech, punctuations, commas, quotations paraphrasing technics you will use. We must note that technical and commercial essays have their writing style, so it is essential to know exactly how to construct and style your essay before embarking on it (EUCLID 2019, 25-26).

4) LATIN EXPRESSIONS AND ABBREVIATIONS

I have never taken a Latin class before. Still, coming into the field of medicine, I have encountered Latin words daily, such as the “A.M” and “P.M” symbol used as a time format, of which many are unaware of the Latin meaning, which is *ante meridiem* (A.M) and *post meridiem* (P.M). Yet, it is worldly used by every English speaker. I realized that many medical prescriptions have Latin abbreviations, though seldomly used; you could see written, p.r., pr, PR which stands for *rectally* in English and *per rectum* in Latin; n.p.o., npo, NPO which stands for *nothing by mouth / not by oral administration* in English and *nil per os* in Latin; p.r.n., prn, PRN which stands for *as needed* in English and *pro re nata* in Latin, just to name a few.

Even in academic writings, unbeknownst to many, Latin abbreviations are so often used that we do not think of them as Latin language; for example (e.g. (*exempli gratia*), i.e. (*id est*), N.B. (nota bene), p.s. (*post scriptum*), vs. (versus), etc. (et cetera). Spoken English has a lot of integrated Latin abbreviations as well; some examples are, cf. which is *confer* in Latin and *compare* in English, and c.v., which is *curriculum vitae* in Latin and *curriculum vitae* in English as well, and the list goes on and on. EUCLID approves Latin abbreviations in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing (e.g., the information in parenthesis).

The language of Latin has had a tremendous effect on the evolution of the English language. According to the Oxford English Dictionary, approximately 50% of all English words are derived from Latin roots. English is my first language but living in this diverse country (USA), I am opportune to borrow words every day due to my day-to-day interactions at my job, school, and my surroundings. A well-known Latin quote is, *veni, vedi, vici* meaning, I came, I saw, I conquered (Suetonius, Iulius37). Julius Caesar specifically wrote these words back in Rome, to describe his quick and decisive victory in 47 BC at the Battle of Zela against King Pharnaces 11 of potus. Latin words usually put the adjective ahead of that preposition, e.g., *Summa Cum Laude*, with the highest praise. Another Latin name worth knowing is; *per annum* meaning, for each year. In this case, one

can say, “I make one hundred and fourth dollars per annum. There is no doubt that the fundamentals in the ACA-401D period one would help me learn more throughout my EUCLID study, and I am looking forward to learning more Latin expressions and abbreviations.

5) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

Growing up in a bilingual country, speaking both English and French languages was a great start for me, although migrating to the United States of America made it a little tricky and frustrating since it became hard for me to differentiate between American and British English. I used to wonder why two words are spelled the same yet sounded so different. It is incorrect to say that one type of English is better than the other or more correct than the other. It is essential to be aware of the differences to focus on the most relevant one depending on your country’s location and what language is being used in writing your essay, especially if I must follow the rules, organization, and writing styles.

American English (US) is currently the dominant English vs. British English (GB) because of their Wealth, Population, Magnitude of higher education, Magnitude of global mass media and media technology influence, etc. (EUCLID 2019, 28). The American accent, spelling, vocabulary, pronunciation, syntax, general usage, and grammar are different from the British. However, American and British English are both Variants of the World English and are similar but different in many ways; for example, in British English, you would say *ageing* vs. *aging* in American English; *Cheque* in British vs. *check* in American. Some words have the same term, sound different but similar spelling and pronunciations like; aluminum-aluminium, Maths-Math, polythene-polyethylene. Both languages have an interesting concept of using the same words to mean different things; for example, in GB ‘trousers’ = US ‘pants’; US ‘pants’ = GB ‘underwear pants’ (EUCLID 2019, 27-35).

Examples of the contrast and similarities of both US and GB English are endless. According to the article, *Differences between British and American English*, “The British introduced the language to the Americas when they reached these lands by sea between the 16th and 17th centuries. At that time, the spelling had not yet been standardized. It took the writing of the first dictionaries to set in stone how these words appeared. In the UK, the dictionary was compiled by London-based scholars. In the United States, the lexicographer was a man named Noah Webster, (E2 Talk, 2020). He allegedly changed how the words were spelled to make the American version different from the British as a way of showing cultural independence from its mother country.” It is no surprise that both US and GB English have both interchanged correspondingly.

6) TYPES OF QUOTATION MARK

These are curly hooks often used to surround sentences and phrases, which shows a person’s exact words. In other words, capturing the author’s comments; for example, my

mom said, “You can do it.” Interestingly, you can write this sentence alternatively as “You can do it,” my mom said; either way, the quotation marks are used here to capture what my mom said and keep it in its original fixed form.

From my google engine internet research, I compiled that Quotation marks are also called inverted commas due to their shape and can either be curly double quotes (“ ”) or straight single quotes (‘ ’). The use of these two types could be slightly complicated, but as a general rule, American writers have always preferred using double quotes meanwhile British writers have usually preferred single quotes for everyday use; Apparently, in recent times, the use of double quotes have become more popular for all writers than its single counterpart quote: Single quotation marks are used to indicate quotations inside of other quotations, and you could rotate the quotations within quotations, alternating between single quote marks and double quote marks for every layer and the sentence would still make sense, but quite frankly it would look extremely messy. Let’s explore an example; “Grace said ‘shut the door’” Nel said. Nel is stating what Grace said, and because Nel is the one speaking, his words go in double quotation marks, and Grace’s in single quotation marks, thereby using the single quotation marks to indicate the quote within the quote.

The use of both types of quotation marks can be used interchangeably, and there are no legal rules of when to apply. Back by popularity, I would mainly use the curly double quote because, in the Turabian’s manual (Eighth Edition), all quotations marks used are in the double quotes style.

7) CONCLUSION

I am pursuing a Doctorate in International Public Health (DIPH). Although I have all the study materials, rules, and regulations to writing a good essay for my Response Paper, I still found this process somewhat challenging. But the silver lining in not knowing it all is that it pushes me to inquire and keep learning. Learning different expressions and how to organize my work in style has always been a significant concern. However, this course, ACA-401D period 1, has introduced me to what I need to do. I appreciate EUCLID’S approach to making this process easy, by providing the templet and the introductory video at the start of the course, presented by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck, a course pack, and how to write a response paper by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma (EUCLID 2020, 2-10).

This course removes any doubts I had about writing an excellent basic English paper and has provided me a strong foundation to build my skills in essay writing. I am content to kick-start this journey with an intensive understanding of the style and formatting of the classic Chicago Manual of style writing, to maintain clarity and consistency with my project. I “would not be caught dead” plagiarizing with all the knowledge I have gathered from this course on how to avoid plagiarism by correctly paraphrasing, citing, and quoting. I am now in full awareness of how American English and British English differ; considering their history, it does not take me aback to realize how different yet similar they are; paying attention to these details would prevent confusion in my writing format. “Lest we forget,” 50% of all English words are from Latin roots, and

as rampant as we use Latin abbreviations, it's a good thing that it is appropriate in footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing.

Abraham Lincoln said, "Give me six hours to chop down a tree, and I will spend the first four sharpening the axe." The time I have put into learning all the fundamentals in the ACA-401D period one has sharpened my axe. I am confident that this program and all the lessons learned from this course will enable me to be successful in EUCLID.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. 2020. *How to Write a Response Paper*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401D/ACA-401DD Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

Brown, Tara. 2014. *Getting to the Heart of Teaching and Learning*. AMLE Magazine, vol. 2, no. 3, Association for Middle Level Education.

Conrad van, Dyk, 2018. *The Nature of Writing*. Associate professor of English: Concordia University of Edmonton.

Thienan, Nguyen. 2020. *Should my child Learn American English or British English?* Everest Education.

Brown, Tara. 2014. *Getting to the Heart of Teaching and Learning*. AMLE Magazine, vol. 2, no. 3, Association for Middle Level Education.

Shanta, Bahadur, Pun. 2014, *Saga of 240/300/900 MW Upper Karnali (KR1A)4,180 MW Upper Karnali Storage Project (KR1B) to be Sacrificed*

Bryson, Bill. 1990. *The Mother Tongue: English and How It Got That Way*. New York: Avon.

2020 British Council. Differences between British and American English. Database online. Available from, British Council Indonesia Foundation

<<https://www.britishcouncilfoundation.id/en/english/articles/british-and-american-english>>. [accessed December 18, 2020].

June Casagrande. 2020. A Word, Please: How to use single, double quotation marks. Journal of the Williamsport Sun-Gazette (July 4), <<https://www.sungazette.com/life/lifestyle-news/2020/07/a-word-please-how-to-use-single-double-quotation-marks/>>. [accessed December 18, 2020]

2020 Goodreads, Inc. The. <<https://www.goodreads.com/quotes/tag/preparation>>
[accessed December 18, 2020]

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D
Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.